

Austria- Ternitz and Jennersdorf

	<i>Community Hub with a Social Coordinator</i>	Create a welcoming space where residents—both new and long-term—can connect, participate in activities, and support local associations. A social coordinator would help match volunteers with local initiatives, strengthen social cohesion, and counteract discrimination.
	<i>Decentralized Health Network</i>	Expand the Raabtal Health Network model, which brings together various health professionals across rural locations. It ensures access to primary care and could include mental health and social support services.
	<i>Women's Empowerment and Support</i>	Support local organizations that help women enter the job market and find community support. These initiatives are especially valuable in areas where traditional roles and isolation limit women's opportunities.
	<i>Affordable and Alternative Housing Models</i>	Promote limited-profit and subsidized housing to offer attractive alternatives to single-family homes. This could include intergenerational or communal housing, especially for older adults. In Ternitz, focus also on renovating aging housing and reducing neighbourhood stigma.
	<i>Inclusive Vocational Training</i>	Offer targeted vocational training for people with special needs, disabilities, or language barriers. This helps address labour shortages while supporting groups often excluded from the job market.

Belgium- Marchienne-au-Pont

	<i>Fighting Slum Landlords</i>	This strategy aims to stop abusive landlords who rent unsafe and overpriced homes to vulnerable people. It suggests using existing laws to check and renovate empty or unfit buildings and create more social housing. The goal is to ensure access to decent housing for all.
	<i>Reopening Community Spaces</i>	This strategy proposes bringing back small local centers where people can meet, do activities, and get support. These spaces can reduce isolation, help with digital skills, and offer youth programs. It's affordable and based on reusing spaces that already exist.
	<i>Digital Help for Everyone</i>	This strategy focuses on giving one-to-one support to people who struggle with digital tools. By training digital helpers and using local centers, it aims to make online services easier to use and reduce social isolation, especially for older or vulnerable people.

Belgium- Couvin

	<p><i>Develop economic activity in concentrated areas</i></p>	<p>Create business areas where companies are grouped together, offer training to local people so they can work there, and make sure public transport connects these areas. This helps reduce unemployment, keeps young people in the area</p>
	<p><i>Improve skills through joint training programs</i></p>	<p>This strategy suggests building strong partnerships between schools, training centres, and companies to help local people gain the skills they need for real jobs.</p>
	<p><i>Set up a community medical centre</i></p>	<p>Set up a medical centre with different professionals (doctors, nurses, therapists, etc.) offering free care. But the big challenge is that few doctors want to move to Couvin, so this plan may need support from higher-level authorities to succeed.</p>

Denmark- Frederikshavn and Morsø

	<p><i>Giving New Life to Empty Buildings</i></p>	<p>This strategy aims to turn abandoned buildings into active community spaces by supporting local associations that can legally purchase and renovate them. With access to external funding and collaboration from municipalities, communities can create local hubs that meet social needs and strengthen local identity.</p>
	<p><i>Making Rural Transport Easier to Use</i></p>	<p>The goal is to improve access to existing flexible transport services by making information clearer and easier to find. Actions include distributing printed guides, including transport info in welcome packs, and appointing local contact persons to help residents who are not digitally connected.</p>
	<p><i>Investing in Fair Rural Transport</i></p>	<p>This strategy calls for long-term investment in rural public transport infrastructure. It argues that mobility is a basic right and should not rely on volunteer solutions. Public authorities must commit to building reliable transport systems that serve ageing and scattered populations fairly.</p>

Greece- Acharnes

	<p><i>Safe and Accessible Mobility</i></p>	<p>Improve everyday mobility in Acharnes by developing a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (ΣΒΑΚ) that guides long-term improvements. This includes repairing damaged roads, building accessible sidewalks with ramps and tactile paving, and creating safe, well-lit routes to schools and public facilities.</p>
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	<p><i>Climate Resilience and Civil Protection</i></p>	<p>Strengthen local capacity to prevent and respond to natural disasters like wildfires and floods, which are increasingly affecting Acharnes. The strategy includes better coordination of existing volunteer groups, improving firebreaks and drainage systems, reforesting vulnerable areas, and involving schools and residents in emergency awareness and planning. The goal is to protect at-risk neighbourhoods and build a culture of shared responsibility.</p>
	<p><i>Aesthetic and Urban Planning Renewal</i></p>	<p>Tackle disorganized urban development and neglected public spaces by launching a Local Urban Plan. This includes renovating parks, squares, and pedestrian areas, and transforming abandoned buildings into community hubs or service centers. Resident participation is key to ensure the regeneration reflects local needs and restores pride in the neighbourhood.</p>
<p>Greece- Pyrgos</p>		
	<p><i>Safe and Accessible Schools</i></p>	<p>Establish a formal inspection and upgrade plan for school buildings to ensure they are safe, accessible, and climate adapted. The strategy includes regular assessments, structural improvements, and better design, responding to strong community concern about deteriorating infrastructure and unsafe environments for children.</p>
	<p><i>Mobility for All</i></p>	<p>Improve Pyrgos' transport connections by renovating the main bus station, creating mini-bus routes to outlying villages, and advocating for the return of train service to Patras and Athens. Complement these with safer sidewalks, better lighting, and public campaigns to promote transport use. The goal is to reduce isolation and make daily mobility easier for everyone.</p>
	<p><i>Clean City with Shared Responsibility</i></p>	<p>This strategy focuses on making Pyrgos cleaner through shared citizen and municipal responsibility. It includes practical upgrades like new or underground garbage bins, especially in problem zones, along with campaigns in schools and neighbourhoods to raise awareness about cleanliness and recycling. A pilot "recycling rewards" initiative encourages active participation.</p>
<p>Italy- Murano and Gennargentu</p>		
	<p><i>Helping Small Towns Get Access to Funding</i></p>	<p>This strategy proposes creating a shared development agency that helps small municipalities apply for and manage public funds. By pooling expert staff like project managers and accountants, it ensures that rural areas can compete for investment and carry out local projects effectively.</p>
	<p><i>Creating Local Listening Spaces</i></p>	<p>To rebuild trust between citizens and institutions, this strategy suggests opening public "listening rooms" in existing municipal buildings. Staffed by civil servants and volunteers, these spaces allow residents—especially older adults—to raise concerns, get guidance, and follow up on local issues in person.</p>
	<p><i>Bringing Public Spaces Back to Life</i></p>	<p>This strategy aims to renovate abandoned public buildings—like schools or sports areas—and turn them into vibrant community hubs. Each project includes a plan co-designed with local groups to ensure the space is used for activities that promote culture, health, and youth participation.</p>

Serbia- Surdulica

Boosting Employment

This strategy aims to create more jobs in Surdulica by bringing new investment into the area and supporting local small businesses. To do this, participants proposed offering financial incentives to attract companies, helping small and medium enterprises (SMEs) with funding, and revitalising agriculture—especially by promoting sustainable farming and involving young people and rural entrepreneurs.

Improving Mobility

The goal of this strategy is to reduce the isolation of Surdulica and make it easier for people to reach jobs, services and other towns. To achieve this, participants suggested rebuilding local roads, creating a bypass around the town to avoid traffic jams, and expanding public transport

Expanding Elderly Care Services

With an ageing population and a lack of family support networks, this strategy calls for investment in home-based care and the development of daycare services for older people

Serbia- Golubac

Expanding and improving tourism

Make better use of Golubac's natural and cultural heritage. The strategy includes improving roads and trails, creating more places to stay, and building a strong local brand. The goal is to offer full experiences that make visitors stay longer and come back again.

Supporting local businesses

To reduce dependence on tourism alone, participants proposed helping small local businesses grow—especially those run by women and young people. The plan includes training, small subsidies, expert advice, and digital mentoring. All these actions would be coordinated by the municipality through a local business support centre.

Revitalising agriculture

People also see great potential in local farming. This strategy includes support for young farmers, modern equipment, and creating cooperatives so that people can work together.

Spain- Montcada

Revitalising 'El Punt' Shopping Centre

This strategy proposes to revitalise an important shopping centre by encouraging business activity and turning it into a multifunctional space for commerce and community life. It includes subsidising new shops, promoting footfall, and creating leisure areas such as benches and rest zones to make the space welcoming.

	<i>Enforcing Environmental Responsibility</i>	This strategy seeks to hold polluting companies accountable by enforcing environmental regulations and generating media and legal pressure. Local associations and environmental groups would lead actions to demand that companies contribute resources to compensate for the area’s waste and pollution.
	<i>Highway Impact Compensation</i>	The strategy calls for compensation from the regional or national government for the negative effects of major highways cutting through Montcada. It proposes political pressure to demand an access point within the town and use funds to improve local conditions. It addresses pollution, disconnection, and fragmented public space caused by overburdening infrastructure.

Spain- San Isidro

	<i>Social Housing Agency Accountability</i>	This strategy aims to improve the management of public housing in San Isidro by demanding greater responsibility from the regional housing agency (AVS). Many residents live in deteriorated buildings, face daily conflicts, and receive no support from the agency. The proposal is to create a local advocacy group made up of neighbours, associations and professionals to collectively push for institutional accountability.
	<i>Let’s beautify the neighbourhood</i>	This strategy proposes small-scale collective actions to improve neglected public spaces—such as cleaning, painting, gardening or revitalising parks. While the physical changes matter, the deeper aim is to strengthen community ties, encourage participation and boost local pride. Activities would be open to all and coordinated by local community teams, creating a shared calendar of events.
	<i>Schools Connected to the Neighbourhood</i>	This strategy seeks to build long-term collaboration between schools and the local community. The idea is to create joint activities—like history workshops, neighbourhood tours, or intergenerational events—that bring students, teachers, families and residents together.

United Kingdom

	<i>Better Transport</i>	This strategy focuses on making mobility easier and more affordable by upgrading local transport infrastructure. It includes road repairs, better bus services, and stronger connections to nearby cities like Manchester and Birmingham. The aim is to reduce isolation and improve access to jobs, education, and essential services.
	<i>Skills for the Future</i>	Develop training and education programs tailored to local job opportunities. In Stoke-on-Trent, this includes craft industries and heritage tourism. In Rochdale, focus is on adult education, ESOL, and intercultural learning. The goal is to reduce unemployment and help people access decent jobs.
	<i>Stronger Social Ties</i>	Support local arts, sports, and youth programs to bring people together and reduce social tensions. These activities are led by local councils and community organisations, but residents are directly involved. The goal is to create trust, shared values, and a stronger sense of belonging.